

Introduction:

- **Greeting, introduce yourself and the research, thank them for coming**

Overview:

- **Describe study, procedure, e.g.:**
We're going to be asking you some questions today about your experiences with ethics in S&P research, from your perspective as author and or reviewer of S&P papers.
- **Reassure them to give honest answers, we aren't judging or testing:**
We're trying to gather your honest thoughts and views on this subject so we'd like to assure you that we aren't trying to test your knowledge or judge your opinion. We may ask you questions on subjects you aren't knowledgeable on, it's perfectly alright to say you are unsure or you don't know.
At times, we may ask you about your own decisions on ethical questions. Here, we want to explicitly acknowledge that we will not judge you on your decision, and your responses will remain anonymous.
You may reassure them that not doing everything perfectly is normal, e.g., "you may not always have time to.."

Consent:

- **Reference the consent form, remind them of confidentiality and opt-out e.g.:**
When taking our survey you signed a consent form, I just wanted to emphasize that what you say to us during the interview will be kept confidential, and you can stop participating at any time, just let us know. If you feel uncomfortable answering any question, we can skip them with no penalty.

Questions before beginning:

- **Ask for questions about the procedure**
Before we start recording and begin the interview, would you like to ask us any questions?

Recording:

- State that you will now turn on the recording, **then do so**, tell them it is now running & re-ask for consent if needed (local / state laws)

1. General Background

1. Can you tell us a bit about your background? How did you get into S&P research, and how long have you been working in that field?
 - a. (if not mentioned) do you have a security/technical background or from a human centered background
 - b. What venues do you publish most at?
2. What roles (author, reviewer..) do you fulfill in the field?
 - a. (if relevant) how long have you been reviewing papers?
3. (idea) How would you define ethics in research?

2. Decision-making concerning Ethics in S&P research

1. In your previous research projects, at which points did you think about ethics?
 - a. (prompt if necessary) e.g. idea, study design, writing, submission, IRB

- b. What prompts you to think about ethics? (e.g., peer review, IRB, a co-author, intrinsic)
 - i. Why does this prompt you to think about ethics?
- 2. What are the main ethics factors that you consider when creating a research project?
- 3. Have you ever struggled with ethical questions during research?
- 4. How have you made decisions about ethical considerations in past projects?
 - a. Have you had disagreements with co-authors about ethics?
- 5. Have you ever had a research question or idea that you did not do because of ethical concerns? (added later)
- 6. Have you ever tried to think about the unintended consequences of your research? Specifically, consequences of your research outcome/ after publication especially in the case of new technologies or methods? (added later)
- 7. When do you consider writing about ethics?
 - a. How did you learn to write about ethics?
 - b. Can you think of situations where writing about ethics is not crucial?
- 8. How did you learn to reason about ethics? (e.g., peer review, personal interest, classes)
- 9. [Reviewers] How do you determine if research was ethical?
- 10. [Reviewers] How do you think authors should present ethics and ethical considerations in papers? (eg. include it in methods, separate section..?)
 - a. Do you have different expectations for different research topics?
 - i. eg. human centered, security, user research, sec vulnerabilities...?
 - b. Do you expect to see specific ethics sections (eg. with title, separate paragraph)?
- 11. Are there differences in how you review papers from different countries?

3. Actions in case of potentially unethical research

- 1. How would you handle negative outcomes of your research?
 - a. Have you ever realized that your research might have adverse impacts? How did you mitigate potential risks?
- 2. (The next questions are about ..)How can harmful or unethical research be handled, at different stages of the publishing process?
 - a. If the research was already done but not published?
 - b. The research is published, but is deemed unethical by (newer) community standards. How should this be handled?
 - c. find an example? (to better explain)
- 3. [(IRB)Reviewers] What feedback do you give authors with (potentially) unethical research?
 - a. Are there specific steps they should take?
- 4. [(IRB)Reviewers] What steps do you take when you identify a study with a negative impact?

4. Personal Experiences with ethics

- 1. Could you recall any research that you might have encountered that you think was unethical and why? Published or unpublished, during peer review?
- 2. Can you remember any important events within the S&P research community regarding ethics? (events that sparked a conversation)
- 3. What did you learn from these experiences?
 - a. Is there something you want to follow or avoid?
 - b. Has this influenced your behavior?
- 4. Have you ever written a paper with an explicit ethics section?
 - a. If you would want to improve your previous papers, what would you do differently? (eg. things to add, highlight, present differently)

5. From whom have you received the most feedback concerning ethics?
 - a. With whom do you talk about ethics the most?
6. Have you received any education concerning ethics (e.g. university classes..)? (prompt if necessary: What kind and how much?)
 - a. Has the education helped/influenced you in your professional life?
7. Have you ever taught ethics to students? (If yes: How?)
8. How are your experiences with your institutional support regarding ethics?
9. [Reviewers] Have you ever rejected (or argued for rejection) a paper because of unethical research or lack of explanation on (ethical) practices?
 - a. Have you discussed the ethics of papers during peer reviews?
 - b. Can you describe the discussion and its outcome? (If you are comfortable and able not to violate the confidentiality of the review process)
10. [Reviewers] In your experience is ethics an important part of paper reviewing?
 - a. Have you witnessed changes in the importance it receives or handling of ethics in the past?

5. Future of ethics in S&P research

1. How well do you think ethics are currently handled?
 - a. What would you change about how ethics is currently handled?
 - b. [Reviewers] What would you improve regarding the reviewing process?
 - c. What could support the development/change of ethics in research?
 - d. Do you think ethics are considered importantly enough?if yes, why? If no, why?)
2. What support would you like to receive in the future, to conduct ethical research?
 - a. And from whom? (IRB, lawyers, other researchers...)
3. [(IRB)Reviewers]What support would you like to receive to review research, specifically concerning ethics?
 - a. And from whom?
4. [(IRB)Reviewers] What recommendations do you have for authors and the S&P research community?

6. Finishing question

1. Now that we talked about ethics a lot, do you think your definition of ethics has changed?
 - a. (if necessary) Would you consider different aspects now regarding negative impacts?
2. Is there anything else related to ethics that you would like to add?